

Humification is a natural, nature-preserving technology that can be used in a closed-loop economy

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The soil is considered as one of the largest carbon reservoirs in the biosphere (1,500 gigatons of carbon). Moreover, the main stable reservoir (at least hundreds and thousands of years) They are humic substances that are formed during the process of humification.

The popular concepts of "non-human" physical stabilization of soil organic matter, based mainly on the process of occluding undecayed organic residues with highly dispersed mineral particles, do not provide long-term stabilization of these residues. Their age, as a rule, does not exceed dozens of years. Whereas humic substances are much older. The process of humification leads to the formation of specific spatially distributed macromolecules of humic substances, which have significantly higher biothermodynamic stability. Even in conditions of an active biological cycle, their age in the soil is 1-3 thousand years.

Humification is the second largest process of transformation of organic matter after photosynthesis. The stability of humic substances as a reservoir of carbon sink is ensured by the biochemical stability of their molecular structure and their connection with the mineral matrix of the soil.

In 2021, IUPAC declared humification the No. 1 promising technology in solving the most important problems of mankind. Currently, humification is considered as an important component of a circular economy and as a promising decarbonization technology. The future belongs to humic substances obtained during the processes of humification of animal by-products, debris and other organic waste and the development of carbon negative eco-adaptive technologies within the framework of "green chemistry" and a closed-loop economy.

Artificial humification of organic waste and the development of carbon negative eco-adaptive technologies within the framework of "green chemistry" and a closed-loop economy is the most important task. Humification should be considered as an important component of the circular economy of a closed cycle

In Russia, this problem is being actively discussed and developed on the basis of the Federal Law regulating the processing of Organic Waste, which entered into force on March 1, 2023. On February 25, 2025, the Public Chamber of the Leningrad Region held a round table "Projects for the processing of organic waste for the purposes of recycling and/or obtaining secondary material resources." Baltic Agrochemical Union produces organic fertilizers using artificial humification technology followed by the addition of biological agents and enzymes. Baltorganic®

On March 27, 2025, the BRICS International Development Organization held an interregional intersectoral meeting on Sustainable Agriculture: a Vector for Fertility. It considered strategies for creating an eco-sustainable closed-loop model based on nature-like technologies and maintaining soil fertility.

On March 26-27, 2025, the VIII specialized conference "Organic Waste Management" was held in Moscow. It considered the use of organic and inorganic waste and fertilizers from them to regulate the fertility of agricultural land.